

The equivalent Formula of reduced Planck constant

HuangShan

(Wuhu Institute of Technology, China, Wuhu, 241003)

Abstract: The equivalent Formula of reduced Planck constant.

Key words: The reduced Planck constant.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\alpha_0] = \frac{(e_0)^2}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(c)(\hbar)}, \\ \frac{(e_0)^2}{4\pi(\epsilon_0)(a_0)^2} = \frac{(m_e)[\alpha_0]^2(c)^2}{(a_0)}, \end{array} \right. \Rightarrow \boxed{(\hbar) = (m_e)[\alpha_0](c)(a_0)}.$$

Where (ϵ_0) is the Vacuum dielectric constant, (c) is the Speed of light, (e_0) is the Elementary charge, $[\alpha_0]$ is the Fine structure constant, (a_0) is the Bohr radius, (m_e) is the Electron rest mass, (\hbar) is the reduced Planck constant.

Reference: none.